

DAMAGE PROGRESSION OF IMPACT DAMAGED MULTI-AXIAL KNITTED CFRP LAMINATE FOR MARINE USE

Hiroshi Saito¹ and Isao Kimpara¹

¹ *Advanced Materials Science R&D Center, Kanazawa Institute of Technology
Yatsukaho 3-1, Hakusan, Ishikawa 924-0838, Japan*

SUMMARY: This study focused to multi-axial knitted fabric which is expected as a thick and high performance reinforcement for large scale composite structures. The effects of impact damage on multi-axial knitted CFRP laminates molded by vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) method were evaluated. Impact damage inside material was evaluated by ultrasonic scanning device and optical cross-sectional observation. Probed images obtained by both non-destructive and destructive methods were compared each other, and internal damage distribution of multi-axial knitted CFRP laminates was clarified. In additionally, residual compressive strength and fatigue property of impact damaged CFRP laminates were evaluated. From the ultrasonic C-scan images and cross-sectional photographs, three-dimensional damage distribution of impacted CFRP laminate was obtained. Also by post impact fatigue (PIF) test, damage progress behavior was observed.

KEYWORDS: carbon multi-axial fabric, impact damage, cross-sectional observation, post impact fatigue, damage growth observation

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP), which have higher specific modulus and specific strength than that of conventional metals, have been applied to the fields of aerospace, marine, automobile and so on. However, not only the costs of materials and of them manufacturing are still more expensive than metals, but also damage initiation and its growth processes are complicated. Especially in the aerospace field, it is well known that a low velocity impact damage which is caused by such as a drop of tools causes the significant reduction of compressive strength [1-3]. Therefore, the prediction of residual strength and the clarification of damage process of CFRP are very important.

A plenty of researches about the damage and fracture mechanism of FRP have been presented. For example, internal damage of FRP impacted was evaluated by non-destructive evaluation devices such as X-ray computer tomography, ultrasonic scanning device and so on. However, major present non-destructive evaluation devices can hardly detect small damages such as cracks. In addition, complex 2-dimensional or 3-dimensional reinforcement preforms are applied to the recent FRP in order to develop the high mechanical performance, so that the evaluation of 3-dimensional distribution of inside damages has been more difficult.

In this study, internal 3-dimensional damage distribution of impacted carbon multi-axial fabric / vinylester laminate was clarified. In addition, the growth behavior of impact damage under cyclic loading of carbon multi-axial fabric / vinylester laminate was focused. Damage observation was conducted by both destructive and non-destructive methods, which are ultrasonic C-scan and direct cross-sectional observation. Probed images obtained by both mentioned methods were compared each other, and internal damage growth behavior of CFRP laminate was clarified.

MATERIALS AND EQUIPMENTS

Materials and Molding Method

Material used is a multi-axial knitted fabric T700S-12K, developed by Toray Industries, Inc, as shown in Fig.1. This fabric consists of 0° and 90° layers joined by polyester knitting fiber each other. Figure 2 shows the schematic image of vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) setting. It is generally more difficult to flow the resin in carbon fiber than in glass fiber. For this reason, a meshing sheet was set on the peel cloth to flow the resin faster in carbon fiber tow. The resin was flown in a meshing sheet at first, and then was flown in carbon fiber.

Fig.1 Schematic of multi-axial knitted fabric.

Fig.2 Schematic of vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) technique.

Experimental Equipments [4]

Schematic of specimen used is shown in Fig.3. Length of specimen is 150mm and gauge length is 50mm. Width is 43mm. A drop weight with a steel semi-spherical tip was used as an impactor. The weight of impactor was 1113.5g and the radius of the tip was 8 mm. The specimen was mounted between the supporting steel plates with cut-out hole of 15mm in radius, and is given impact energy directly using the impactor. Impact loading of 1J per 1mm thickness was applied to the center of specimens by impactor with 8mm tip radius. Impact damage in specimen is observed and characterized by ultrasonic C-scan method and direct cross-sectional observation method. In order to characterize the impact damage on CFRP laminate, both images observed by ultrasonic C-scan device and cross-sectional observation were compared and integrated as shown in Fig.4. This figure shows the flow in the

characterization methodology of the impact damage on CFRP laminate. Both observation methods give different plane information each other about the impact damage, and information obtained is evaluated synthetically. Finally the three-dimensional damage distribution image is estimated.

Compressive strength after impact (CAI) and post-impact fatigue (PIF) properties were evaluated. In this study, CAI and PIF tests were conducted with same specimen level as shown in Fig.3. Figure 5 shows a fixture for CAI test. Gauge length was 50mm. Compressive load was applied by Servopulser EHF-EB100kN-20L (Shimadzu Co., Ltd.). Test speed of CAI was 1.0mm/min. In PIF tests, stress ratio R was -1, that is, tension-compression test.

Fig.3 Dimension of the specimen.

Fig.4 Three-dimensional characterization of the impact damage inside laminate.

Fig.5 Fixture for CAI test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Evaluation of Impact Damage inside CFRP Laminate

Ultrasonic C-scan images of the impact damaged multi-axial stitched CFRP laminate were shown in Fig.6. Here the impact point is the center of these images. Ultrasonic scanning was conducted to the 5 different depths of a laminate. Two fan-shaped damages which spread in the 0° direction symmetrically considering the impact point were observed near the impact side. Damages spread in the 90° direction in the middle layer, and damage spreading direction changed in 0° direction again at the bottom side of laminate. Accordingly, the damage area detected by ultrasonic C-scan might spread along the direction of fiber bundle which constitutes each layer.

Fig.6 Ultrasonic C-scope images of multi- axial stitched CFRP laminate after impact test.

Both ultrasonic C-scan images and cross-sectional images observed by optical microscope were compared in Fig.7. In this figure, cross-sectional images were divided in three-parts as upper, middle and bottom as shown in Fig.7(a), and each part was compared with ultrasonic C-scan images as shown in Fig.7(b). Consequently correspondence between the damage distribution observed by optical microscope and ultrasonic C-scan images was recognized. However, especially in upper and middle parts, delamination area observed in cross-sections was larger than that in ultrasonic C-scan images. This fact means that the damage, especially delamination, observed by ultrasonic C-scan was comparatively thick ones, and thin delamination was not detected. Further between of upper and middle delaminations, multiple transverse cracks existed, and they must affect on the damage tolerance performance of CFRP laminate.

In order to make a three-dimensional damage model of impact damaged multi-axial stitched CFRP laminate, location of the delamination and transverse crack was determined by the results observed by ultrasonic C-scan and cross-sectional observation. Figure 8 shows a

damage model made by mentioned method. Fan-shape delaminations progressed in between 0° and 90° fiber bundles of each layer, and their progress direction was rotated by a unit of 90° degrees. Transverse cracks progressed from the edge of delamination located in between 2nd and 3rd layers.

(a) distribution of damaged area

(b) ultrasonic C-scan images corresponding to the damage distribution observed in the cross sections

Fig.7 Comparison between damage areas obtained by the cross-sectional observation and the ultrasonic C-scan.

Fig.8 Three dimensional images estimated by the cross-sectional observation of the impact damage on CFRP laminates.

Damage Progress in Post-Impact Fatigue Test

Figure 9 shows the results of CAI test. Applied impact energy levels were following four; 0.5J/mm, 1.0J/mm, 1.5J/mm and 2.0J/mm, and CAI strength was in inverse proportion to impact energy. However, specimens impacted showed drastic decrease of compression strength, for example CAI strength of specimen applied 1J/mm showed 225MPa, which is approximately 35% of compression strength of no-impact material, 680MPa. Figure 10 shows the results of PIF test. Arrow in this figure means that specimens did not failed until 1,000,000 cycles. Scatter is very large for this material, however, stress and number of cycle showed almost linear relation at least by 1,000,000 cycles. For damage growth observation, a specimen which applied fatigue stress level of 88% of CAI strength was used. Fatigue test was stopped 82,000 cycles, which cycle number is about 90% of the failure cycle number of this specimen.

Fig.9 Results of compression after impact (CAI) tests.

Fig.10 Results of post-impact fatigue (PIF) tests.

Figure 11 shows the ultrasonic C-scan images before and after fatigue test. Load is applied in horizontal direction in these images. It is clear that damage progressed in load direction. Figure 12 shows the cross-sectional photographs of specimen with emphasized damage before and after fatigue test. In this figure, load was applied in horizontal direction. In the photograph of specimen after fatigue, many transverse cracks were observed. Figure 13 shows extension photographs of cross section of specimen after fatigue. Schematic images in the right hand in Fig.13 were the damaged area observed by C-scan shown in Fig.11. In schematic images, Gray area indicates damage caused by impact, and black area indicates damage progressed by fatigue. Broken lines in schematic image show the location of cross sections observed. Delamination growth in load direction is observed in Fig.13(a). (1) in this figure shows delamination caused by impact, and progressed delamination indicated by (2) is caused by transverse crack caused by fatigue. In Fig.13(b), Cracks near the impact point with 45 degrees to horizontal direction indicated by (3), which is caused by impact, were joined with crack propagation indicated by (4). From these results, the damage progress modes of multi-axial stitched CFRP laminate used in this study is summarized as follows; (i) delamination in loading direction was progressed from the end of transverse cracks, and (ii) cracks caused by impact were joined by crack propagation at the impact point.

(a) impact damage only

(b) after 82,000 cycles

Fig.11 Ultrasonic C-scan images of a specimen before and after PIF tests.

Fig.12 Impact damage and damage progressed by fatigue on the cross sections.

Fig.13 Damage progressed by fatigue after impact.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the impact damage and its growth behavior of T700 multi-axial stitched CFRP laminates was evaluated based on non-destructive and destructive observation methods. From the ultrasonic C-scan images and cross-sectional photographs, three-dimensional impact damage model of multi-axial stitched CFRP laminate was obtained. After fatigue test, impact damage, especially delamination in load direction, progressed from transverse cracks caused by fatigue. In addition, cracks near the impact point caused by impact were joined with crack propagation by fatigue.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank the Office of Naval Research for supporting this work through an ONR award (N000140110949) with Dr. Yapa Rajapakse as the ONR Program Officer.

The authors thank Professor Richard Christensen at Stanford University as the consultant of this project and Toray Industries Inc. as the supplier of CFRP laminates and carbon fabrics.

REFERENCES

1. Ishai, O. and Shragai, A., "Effect of impact loading on damage and residual compressive strength of CFRP laminated beams", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 14, 1990, pp.319-337.
2. Ogihara, S., Kobayashi, A. and Tanaka, T., "Microscopic damage induced by dropweight impact associated with attributed residual compressive strength in CFRP laminated composites", *Journal of Japan Society of Mechanical Engineering Part A*, Vol. 63, No. 611, 1996, pp.1505-1510.
3. Papanicolaou, G.C. and Stavropoulos, C.D., "New approach for residual compressive strength prediction of impacted CFRP laminates", *Composites*, Vol. 26, 1995, pp.517-523.
4. Yamaguchi, K and Kimpara, I., "Damage observation and simulation of woven fabric CFRP for clarification of damage mechanism", *Materials System*, Vol. 21, 2002, pp.27-39.